

Calculation of the Size, b^* and Dipolemoment, G^* of the Active Group in the Activated Complex in Ion-Dipole type of Reactions in Solution

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Laidler and Landskroener⁹ have derived an equation for calculating b^* , the size of the active group of an activated complex in ion-dipolar molecule type of reactions in solution, in which the transition state is highly polarized. They have calculated G^* theoretically by assuming a specific model of the transition state and the distribution of charges within the molecule. An attempt has been made to calculate b^* and G^* directly without any assumption about the model of the transition state, on the basis of the variation of rate coefficient in a binary solvent mixture.

THEORETICAL expression for the influence of the solvent on electrostatic forces which modify rate processes between ions and dipolar molecules have been a field of interest for several groups of workers.¹⁻³ Laidler and Landskroener⁹ in an attempt to study solvent effect in ion-dipole molecule type of reactions in solution, have successfully related the dielectric constant of the medium with the specific rate constant in a binary solvent mixture. Their equation for a univalent ion reacting with a dipolar molecule is :

$$\ln k = \ln k_0 + \frac{e^2}{2kT} (1/D - 1) (1/b_A - 1/b^* + 3e^2/8kT (2/D - 1) (-G^*/b^{*3}) \dots \dots (i)$$

Where b_A = the size of the reactant ion;

b^* = the size of the active group of the activated complex in the reaction;

G^* = the number proportional to the dipole moment of the active group of the activated complex in the reaction.

The other terms have their usual significance.

On plotting $\log k$ against $1/D$ they obtained a straight line with slope, 'm', given by the expression: $m = \frac{e^2}{2.303 (2kT)} [1/b_A - 1/b^* - 3G^*/2b^{*3}] \dots (ii)$ Laidler and Landskroener pointed out that in order to evaluate b^* and G^* a definite model of the activated complex has to be constructed along with an arbitrary distribution of charges. Thus, for example, in acid hydrolysis of ester, they supposed, a simultaneous attack of hydronium ion on the alcoholic oxygen atom and of a water molecule on carbonyl carbon atom. In basic hydrolysis a simultaneous attack of a hydroxide ion on carbonyl carbon atom and a water molecule on the alcoholic oxygen atom were proposed. Regarding the distribution of charges, the charge transference on the activated complex was assumed to be half of the total charge transference in the complete reaction. And thus the value of G^* can be calculated with the help of

Legendre polynomials :

$$G^* = e_1^2 r_1^2 + e_2^2 r_2^2 + e_3^2 r_3^2 + 2e_1 e_2 r_1 r_2 p_1(x)_{1,2} + 2e_1 e_3 r_1 r_3 p_1(x)_{1,3} + 2e_2 e_3 r_2 r_3 p_1(x)_{2,3} + \dots \dots (iii)$$

Where $p_1(x)_{1,2}$ is the cosine of the angle subtended by the charges e_1 and e_2 at the centre of the sphere and r_1 and r_2 are their distances from that point. The value, G^* thus calculated was assumed to be constant for a given reaction and was inserted in equation (ii) for the evaluation of b^* .

Although Laidler-Landskroener equation has been of much use in the field, the treatment for evaluation of G^* is rather difficult to apply and required a definite model of transition state for each of the reaction. Also it is not convincing to assume the same value of G^* in different solvent mixtures as G^* is bound to change with change of the solvent composition. This prompted the present authors to propose an alternative method, in the form of two separate equations, for evaluating b^* and G^* without any assumption of the model of the activated complex or the distribution of charge over it. The values of b^* and G^* obtained by this method explain the solvent effects very satisfactorily.

An alternative method : This method is based on deducing two separate equations from Laidler-Landskroener equation relating the specific rate with the dielectric constant. Their equation for the specific rate constant of a bimolecular reaction consisting of an ion and a dipolar molecule is given in equation (i). Assuming that k_0 is the specific rate constant in an ideal solution and rearranging equation (i) we get, $\log k = \log k_0 + \frac{1}{2.303} \frac{e^2}{2kT} [(1/b_A - 1/b^* - 3G^*/2b^{*3})(1/D) + (1/b^* - 1/b_A + 3G^*/4b^{*3})] \dots (iv)$ Assuming that the plot of $\log k$ against $1/D$ has a slope m and an intercept with the axis of $\log k$ from the origin is equal to c we get,

$$m = (1/b_A - 1/b^* - 3G^*/2b^{*3}) \frac{1}{2.303} \frac{e^2}{2kT} \dots (v)$$

$$\text{and } c = \log k_0 + (1/b^* - 1/b_A + 3G^*/4b^{*3}) \frac{1}{2.303} \frac{e^2}{2kT} \dots (vi)$$

Putting A in place of $(1/2.303)(e^2/2kT)$ and then

rearranging,

$$1/b_A - 1/b^* - 3G^*/2b^{*3} = m/A \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(vii)}$$

$$1/b^* - 1/b_A + 3G^*/4b^{*3} = (c - \log k_o)/A \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(viii)}$$

On adding equations (vii) and (viii), we get,

$$-3G^*/4b^{*3} = (m + c - \log k_o)/A \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(ix)}$$

Assuming the dielectric constant of ideal solution to be D_o we get, $\log k_o = m/D_o + c \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(x)}$

Putting the value of $\log k_o$ in equation (ix) we get,

$$G^*/b^{*3} = -(4/3)(m/A)[(D_o - 1)/D_o] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(xi)}$$

Substituting the value of G^*/b^{*3} in equation (vii) we get, $(1/b_A - 1/b^*) = -(m/A)[(D_o - 2)/D_o] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(xii)}$

Using equations (xi) and (xii) the value of b^* and G^* can be calculated from the knowledge of the slope of the graph and the dielectric constant of the ideal solution.

Further refinement in these equations have been achieved by taking into consideration the dielectric constant of the solute molecules too. These equations are fundamentally based on Kirkwood's expression^{1,2} for activity co-efficient of spherical solute molecules with a particular distribution of charges, which assumes arbitrarily that the dielectric constant of the solute is two. It has been stated that its actual value does not affect the result, as it is much smaller than the dielectric constant of the medium. If one takes into consideration the dielectric constant of the solute also, equations (xi) and (xii) can be modified as follows;

$$G^*/b^{*3} = -(2/3)[(1+d)/d][(D_o - 1)/D_o]m/A \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(xiii)}$$

$$(1/b_A - 1/b^*) = [(1+d - D_o)/dD_o]m/A \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(xiv)}$$

where $2d$ is the dielectric constant of the solute.

Now it is obvious that in a high dielectric medium the factor $(1+d - D_o)/D_o$ is little affected by a small variation in D_o . In case of ethyl acetate as solute, a variation from 20 to 80 in the value of D_o causes a variation in the value of $(1+d - D_o)/D_o$ from 0.31 to 0.29 only. Therefore the dielectric constant of ideal solution may safely be taken equal to the dielectric constant of water.

Calculation and Results

The dielectric constant of ethyl acetate is 6.4 at 25°, therefore $d=3.2$. Assuming the variation in the size of OH to be small and using its value equal to 1.4 Å (Buchanan and Hamann)¹⁰ as used by Laidler and Landskroener the value of b^* and G^* can be calculated with the help of equations (xiii) and (xiv). Thus applying these two equations for alkaline hydrolysis of esters and using the value of 'm' from (a) Laidler and Landskroener experiment⁹ for ethyl acetate and from (b) Nayak and Rout's experiment¹¹ for ethyl cinnamate, the different values of b^* and G^* have been calculated in various solvent mixtures which have noted in Tables—1 and 2.

TABLE 1

b^* and G^* for alkaline hydrolysis of Ethyl acetate at 25°.

Solvent mixture	Slope ⁹	b^* in Å	$G^* \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^2$
Water-dioxane	-24	1.52	0.60
Water-acetone	-32	1.57	0.97
Water-isopropyl alcohol	-50	1.68	1.70
Water t-butyl alcohol	-61	1.76	2.38
Water n-butyl alcohol	-71	1.86	3.41
Water-ethyl alcohol	-96	2.01	6.10

TABLE 2

b^* and G^* for alkaline hydrolysis of Ethyl cinnamate at 25°.

Solvent mixture	Slope ¹¹	b^* in Å	$G^* \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^2$
Water-alcohol	-96	2.05	5.89
Water-acetone	-68	1.81	2.81

Discussion

It is generally observed that the rate of many reactions, such as hydrolysis of esters and amides^{9,12}, are very sensitive to the dielectric constant of the medium. Their specific rate varies linearly with the dielectric constant of the binary solvent mixture, specially when one of the components is kept in excess. Any ion-dipole type of reaction, with transition state highly polarized can now be used to evaluate the size and the charge separation of the active group in the activated complex with the help of the proposed equations.

As the plot of the slope of $\log k$ against $1/D$ is found experimentally to be constant, it is evident from the proposed equations that b^* and G^* are constants in a particular binary solvent. This constancy of the above parameters has been explained on the basis of selective solvation effect by more polar solvent as suggested by Hynes and co-workers¹³ and further supported by the study of other phenomena like N.M.R.¹⁴ etc.

The theoretical value of G^* calculated by Laidler and Landskroener from alkaline hydrolysis of ethyl acetate is $5.4 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$. The value of G^* thus calculated was used for all binary solvents. This does not appear convincing, since G^* is bound to change with the nature of the constituents of the binary solvent. Tables 1 and 2 show the value of G^* calculated from the proposed equations. It varies from $0.60 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$ to $6.10 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$. The variation of G^* and b^* depends much on the extent of solvation by the polar constituent of the solvents. Here in all binary solvent pairs water has been used as a common constituent in excess and therefore it is natural to assume that the solvation of the transition state is by water molecules alone. The second constituent of the solvent mixture acts as desolvating agent which is reflected in the variation of b^* and G^* in different solvent pairs. From data calculated by the present authors it appears that desolvation by dioxane, an aprotic solvent, is much greater than by protic solvents like alcohols. It has been assumed that the size of OH^- is 1.4 Å in all binary solvent mixtures. The validity of this assumption lies in the fact that H_2O molecules are firmly bonded with this group due to its greater charge density in comparison to the transition state. Further investigations are in progress for future communication.

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R. C. JHA, LALLAN SINGH & S. N. DAS : CALCULATION OF THE SIZE, B^* & DIPOLEMOMENT G^*

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